

**STUDIES ON BIOSYNTHESIZED COPPER OXIDE AND ZINC OXIDE
NANOPARTICLES USING AQUEOUS LEAF EXTRACT OF *PLUMERIA
RUBRA* AND *RIVINIA HUMILIS* AND ANALYSIS OF THEIR
MOSQUITOCIDAL ACTIVITY AGAINST *AEDES AEGYPTI***

DISSERTATION

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in
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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the dissertation entitled “**Studies on biosynthesized copper oxide and zinc oxide nanoparticles using aqueous leaf extract of *Plumeria rubra* and *Rivinia humilis* and analysis of their mosquitocidal activity against *Aedes aegypti*”** is a bonafide work done by **E. Agnita Sharon** in the Department of Zoology, University of Madras, Guindy campus, Chennai-600 025. This dissertation has not formed the basis for the award of any Degree, Diploma, Associateship, Fellowship or other similar title.

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DECLARATION

I, **E. Agnita Sharon**, hereby declare that this dissertation entitled “**Studies on biosynthesized copper oxide and zinc oxide nanoparticles using aqueous leaf extract of *Plumeria rubra* and *Rivinia humilis* and analysis of their mosquitocidal activity against *Aedes aegypti*”** submitted for the award of the degree of Master of Philosophy, is a record of independent research work done under the guidance of **Dr. R. Manikandan**, Department of Zoology, University of Madras, Guindy Campus, Chennai-600025, during the academic year 2018-2019.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Vector-borne diseases has become a major threat to the social and economical status of society. Mosquitoes have been considered to be the most important vector, transmitting dreadful diseases across the world (Kundsén and Slooff, 1992; Klempner *et al.*, 2007). Therefore, mosquito control continues to be an important method in controlling as well as preventing mosquito-borne diseases (Nauen, 2007; Billingsley *et al.*, 2008; Midega *et al.*, 2010).

Aedes aegypti is an important vector for various diseases such as yellow fever, dengue, dengue hemorrhagic fever, and chikungunya. Over 30 million population worldwide have been affected by such diseases (Chakaravati and Kumaria, 2005). This species of mosquito is commonly found in places with stagnant waters, such as pots, tins, and tyres etc. This mosquito is a tropical and subtropical species widely distributed around the world, mostly between latitudes 35°N and 35°S (WHO, 2012). Control of this mosquito in aquatic medium is a highly warranted and effective method in terms of public health (Koodalingam *et al.*, 2011). *Aedes aegypti* transmits the various serotypes of the dengue virus to humans through the bites of mosquitoes. During feeding, the dengue virus is injected into the blood stream of humans. The virus infects the mosquito mid-gut and subsequently spreads over a period of 8-12 days. After this extrinsic incubation period, the virus can be transmitted to other humans during subsequent probing or feeding. The extrinsic incubation period is influenced partly by environmental conditions, especially ambient temperature. Thereafter, the mosquito remains infective for the rest of its life (WHO, 2009).

Extensive use of harmful chemicals and pesticides has led to environmental and health concerns, widespread development of resistance by mosquitoes. and unwanted toxic or lethal

effects on non-target organisms (Roberts and Andre, 1994; Milam *et al.*, 2000; Nauen, 2007). These are a serious of drawbacks to the use of synthetic insecticides. Therefore, the recent studies focus on the mosquito control programme with emphasis on eco-friendly, biodegradable plant-based compounds in controlling vector-borne diseases (Koodalingam *et al.*, 2011).

Green technology or green synthesis using plants has been increasing due to its various properties, such as eco-friendly, non-toxic, and economically advantageous over conventional techniques by offering natural capping agents in the form of proteins and amino acids (Salam *et al.*, 2014). The development of green processes for the synthesis of nanoparticles has been evolving into an important branch of nanotechnology as green nanotechnology deals with the safe and eco-friendly methods for nanomaterials fabrication, which is considered an alternative to conventional physical and chemical methods (Mohanpuria *et al.*, 2008). In the field of herbal medicine intersecting with nanotechnology, this technique involves the use of nanoparticles by employing plants for large-scale synthesis and production. Plants are known to possess various therapeutic compounds that are generally used for traditional medicine (Kavitha *et al.*, 2013).

Biological entities possess a huge potential for the production of nanoparticles. Biogenic reduction of metal precursors to corresponding nanoparticles is eco-friendly (Jayaseelan *et al.*, 2012), sustainable (Gopinath *et al.*, 2014), free of chemical contamination (Chandran *et al.*, 2006; Huang *et al.*, 2007), less expensive (Mittal *et al.*, 2013), and can be used for mass production. Thus, biologically synthesized nanoparticles are gaining more importance and prove to be an alternative to the chemical method.

In recent years, plant-fabricated nanoparticles have been studied for their highly effective mosquitocidal properties. The green biosynthesis of nanoparticles is advantageous over chemical and physical methods, since it is cheap, a single-step process, and does not require high pressure, energy, temperature, or the use of highly toxic chemicals. It has been hypothesized that the biotoxicity against mosquito instars may be due to the ability of nanoparticles to penetrate through the exoskeleton of mosquito larvae. In the intracellular space, nanoparticles can bind to sulphur from proteins or to the phosphorus from DNA, leading to the rapid denaturation of organelles and enzymes. Subsequently, the decrease in membrane permeability and disturbance in proton motive force may lead to loss of cellular function and cell death (Benelli, 2016).

In insects, esterases are involved in several physiological functions such as reproduction, digestion, metabolism of juvenile hormone, and moulting (Jones and Brancoft, 1986; Lassiter *et al.*, 1995; Shanmugavelu *et al.*, 2000). It also plays an important role in the detoxification of synthetic chemicals to less toxic metabolites (Wheelock *et al.*, 2005). Therefore, such enzymes can be used as reliable markers to assess the impact of toxicants on a range of test organisms (Mora *et al.*, 1999; Fourcy *et al.*, 2002; Wheelock *et al.*, 2005; Smirle *et al.*, 2010).

Phosphatases are another potential marker for analysing the deleterious impact of various synthetic chemicals on target pests, as it is known to play a diverse role in various physiological processes in insects (Walter and Schütt, 1974; Asakura, 1978; Eguchi, 1995; Majerus *et al.*, 1999). Esterases and phosphatases have been widely used as an accurate and sensitive marker to check the toxicity of chemical and botanical insecticides (Smirle *et al.*, 1996, 2010; Galloway *et al.*, 2002; Bonacci *et al.*, 2004; Shekari *et al.*, 2008). It has been an

increased interest in the application of biocides with several advantages over synthetic chemical insecticides and their mode of action on mosquito pests.

The plant *Plumeria rubra* Linn is a deciduous tree with thick leaves and is widely distributed, rather than in moist gardens, in lawns and in open plantations. It grows up to a height of 3.5 to 6 m (Manisha, 2016), and about eight species of *Plumeria rubra* (L.) occur in India (Baghel *et al.*, 2010). According to Ayurveda reports, the root of *Plumeria rubra* seems to be bitter in taste, possessing few medicinal properties such as carminative, thermogenic, and laxative activities. Leaves are used for inflammation, rheumatism, antibacterial activity, bronchitis, cholera, cold, cough, antipyretic, antifungal, stimulant, etc. (Rastogi *et al.*, 2006). The latex of the plant has been used to synthesize nanoparticles (Patel *et al.*, 2012). But the potential of leaves in the synthesis of nanoparticles has not been studied.

The plant *Rivina humilis* (Phytolaccaceae), commonly called pigeon berry, is a wild herbaceous bushy perennial. The plant is found in colonies that grow on various types of shaded soils up to a height of 120 cm (Swarbick, 1997; Wealth of India, 2008). It is an herbaceous plant or small shrub usually growing about 0.6 to 1 m tall, that prefers damp and shady habitats. Its medicinal uses include the treatment of wounds, cuts, and other skin ailments. The leaves are used for the treatment of inflammation in the stomach, joints, and wound healing mechanisms (Tseng *et al.*, 2008; Mabblerley, 2008; Dequan, 2013; Jasbirbagga, 2017). It is primarily used for cleaning block tubes, infertility, or any womb-related problems. It is also used for menstrual flow problems. Although many investigations have been carried out on the pharmacognasy and phytochemistry of this plant, its potential in the areas of nanotechnology is yet to be revealed.

The present investigation deals with the unreported green chemistry route for the synthesis of copper oxide and zinc oxide nanoparticles using leaf extract derived from *Plumeria rubra* and *Rivina humilis* and its mosquitocidal activities.

Objectives of the present study

- Synthesis of copper oxide and zinc oxide nanoparticles using the aqueous leaf extracts of *Plumeria rubra* and *Rivina humilis*, respectively.
- Characterization of the biologically synthesized copper oxide and zinc oxide nanoparticles by using UV spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction, field emission scanning electron microscope, energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy, and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy.
- Elucidation of the anti-mosquito effect of these two nanoparticle preparations against the fourth instar larvae of *Aedes aegypti*, as well as analysis of their impact on enzyme activities such as acetylcholinesterase, carboxylesterase, alkaline phosphatase, and histopathological changes in the target mosquito larvae.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

1.0 MATERIALS

1.1 Fine chemicals

Copper sulphate, Zinc nitrate, and *P*-nitrophenyl phosphate were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, USA (99.5% pure). Acetylthiocholine iodide, DTNB reagent (5-5'-dithiobis 2-nitrobenzoic acid), fast blue B salt, α - or β -naphthyl acetate, and α -naphthyl phosphate were obtained from Himedia (Mumbai, India). All other chemicals and reagents used were commercially available and of the highest analytical grade.

1.2 Collection of plants

The leaves of *Plumeria rubra* and *Rivinia humilis* were collected from the University of Madras, Guindy campus, Chennai, India, and authenticated by plant taxonomists.

1.3 Preparation of aqueous extracts

Aqueous extract of *Plumeria rubra* and *Rivina humilis* was prepared by using 10g of shade dried leaves and 25g of fresh leaves, respectively, which were then grinded under laboratory conditions using an electric mixer, followed by boiling with 100 ml of double-distilled water at 60°C for 10 min and 30 min, respectively. These extracts were filtered using Whatman filter paper no.1 and used for further experiments.

1.4 Mosquito collection and rearing

Mosquito *Aedes aegypti* larvae were collected from water tanks, broken bottles, and small water courses. They were maintained at the temperature of $28 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $80 \pm 10\%$ RH (Relative Humidity) under 12 hour light and dark photoperiod cycle. The larvae were fed a dog biscuit and a brewer's yeast powder mixture in a 3:1 ratio in the laboratory. After five days, adult male

mosquitoes were fed a 10% sucrose solution. The emerging female mosquitoes obtain a blood meal from a white albino rat for 2-3 h for egg production (Kamaraj *et al.*, 2008).

1.5 Other insects used as non-target organisms

The larvae of *Chironomous costatus* were collected from Kolathur, Chennai, and maintained under laboratory conditions. The fourth instar was identified, separately collected, and immediately used for bioassays.

2.0 BUFFERS AND OTHER SOLUTIONS

2.1 Preparation of copper sulphate (5 mM; CuSO₄)

0.12 g of copper sulphate was dissolved in 100 ml of distilled water to obtain a concentration of 5 mM copper sulphate.

2.2 Preparation of zinc nitrate (35 mM; ZnNO₃)

1g of zinc nitrate was weighed and added directly to 100 ml of aqueous extract.

2.3 Phosphate buffer (100mM; pH 7.0, 7.5)

Solution A:

1.56 g of sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate was dissolved in 100ml of double-distilled water.

Solution B:

1.41 g of disodium hydrogen orthophosphate was dissolved in 100ml of double-distilled water.

39 ml of solution A was mixed with 61ml of solution B, and its pH was adjusted to 7.0 using solution A or B.

2.4 Phosphate buffer (20mM; pH 7.0)

Solution A:

0.310 g of sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate was dissolved in 100ml of double-distilled water.

Solution B:

0.56 g of disodium hydrogen orthophosphate was dissolved in 200ml of double-distilled water.

78 ml of solution A was mixed with 122ml of solution B, and its pH was adjusted to 7.0 using solution A or B.

2.5 Acetylthiocholine iodide

17.35mg of acetylthiocholine iodide were dissolved in 5ml of double-distilled water to get a final concentration of 12.5 mM acetylthiocholine iodide.

2.6 5-5' dithiobis 2 nitrobenzoic acid (DTNB) reagent

19.815 mg of DTNB was dissolved in 5ml of phosphate buffer (100 mM; pH 7.0) to get a final concentration of 10mM DTNB.

2.7 Alpha-naphthyl acetate

4.65 mg of α -naphthyl acetate were dissolved in 1ml of acetone to obtain a concentration of 25mM. This was then made up to 100ml with phosphate buffer (20mM; pH 7.0) to get a final concentration of 250 μ M α -naphthyl acetate in 1%acetone.

2.8 Beta-naphthyl acetate

4.65 mg of β -naphthyl acetate were dissolved in 1ml of acetone to obtain a concentration of 25mM. This was then made up to 100ml with phosphate buffer (20mM; pH 7.0) to get a final concentration of 250 μ M β -naphthyl acetate in 1%acetone.

2.9 SDS 3.3% +Fast blue B0.3%

1.65 g of sodium lauryl sulphate (SDS) was dissolved in 50ml of phosphate buffer (20mM; pH 7.0), and 150 mg of fast blue B salt was added to the solution. The solution was stirred well for 1 hour at RT. The undissolved dye particles were filtered using Whatman No. 1 filter paper. This solution was freshly prepared before use.

2.10 Alpha-naphthol standard

18.02 mg of α -naphthol were dissolved in 2.5 ml of acetone to get a final concentration of 50mM α -naphthol. From this stock solution, the following concentrations of α -naphthol were prepared by appropriate dilution of 100,200,300, 400, and 500 μ M using double-distilled water.

2.11 Beta-naphthol standard

43.25mg of β -naphthol were dissolved in 3.0 ml of acetone to get a final concentration of 100 mM β -naphthol. From this stock solution, the following concentrations of β -naphthol were prepared by appropriate dilution of 100,200,300, 400, and 500 μ M using double-distilled water.

2.12 Sodium acetate buffer (50 mM; pH 4.6)

0.41g of sodium acetate trihydrate was dissolved in 50 ml of double-distilled water, and the pH was adjusted to 4.6 with 0.75 ml of acetic acid in 50 ml of distilled water. The final volume was made to 100 ml.

2.13 Tris-HCl buffer (50 mM; pH 8.0)

3.35g of tris (hydroxymethyl) aminomethane was dissolved in 500 ml of double-distilled water to obtain 50mM tris. The pH of this solution was adjusted to pH 8 using 2N HCl.

2.14 Neutral buffered formalin (pH 7.0)

0.4 g of sodium phosphate monobasic, 0.6 g of sodium phosphate dibasic were dissolved in double-distilled water, 10 ml of formaldehyde was added, and the solution was finally made to 100 ml using double-distilled water.

3.0 METHODS

3.1 Phytochemical screening

The aqueous leaf extract of *P. rubra* and *R. humilis* was used for analysis of various phytochemicals such as alkaloids, carbohydrates, flavonoids, steroids, phenols, saponins, tannins, and glycosides.

(i) Detection of saponin

5 ml of solution and an equal volume of distilled water were added and shaken vigorously for the formation of a stable, persistent froth.

(ii) Detection of tannins

2 ml of extract and a few drops of 0.1% ferric chloride solution were added. The formation of green precipitate indicates the presence of tannins.

(iii) Detection of alkaloids

2 ml of the extract, 2 ml of 1% HCl were added and kept in a water bath, and then a drop of Wagner's reagent was added. The formation of brown precipitate revealed the presence of alkaloids.

(iv) Detection of reducing sugars

Fehling's test: 1 ml of extract was boiled with 1 ml of Fehling's solution A and B. The colour change was observed. A red precipitate indicates the presence of carbohydrates.

(v) Detection of flavonoids

2ml of 10% lead acetate and 2ml of plant extract were added. The presence of yellow precipitate indicates the presence of flavonoids.

(vi) Detection of glycosides

2 ml of glacial acetic acid containing 0.2% FeCl_3 was added to 5 ml of plant extract, which was transferred to 1 ml of conc. H_2SO_4 . Formation of a brown ring at the interface indicates the presence of glycosides.

(vii) Detection of steroids

3 ml of plant extract, 2 ml of glacial acetic acid, and 2 ml of conc. H_2SO_4 was added. The appearance of green colour indicates the presence of steroids.

(viii) Detection of terpenoids

3 ml of conc. H_2SO_4 was added along the sides of the test tube, carefully containing 5 ml of extract and 2 ml of CHCl_3 . Formation of reddish brown colour at the interface indicates the presence of terpenoids.

(ix) Detection of phenols

1 ml of extract and a few drops of 5% FeCl_3 were added. To this, a few drops of conc. H_2SO_4 was added carefully. Formation of deep blue black colour indicates the presence of phenols.

4.0 Characterization of synthesized CuONPs and ZnONPs

4.1 Synthesis of copper oxide nanoparticles (CuONPs) and zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnONPs)

For the synthesis of CuONPs, 10 ml of aqueous leaf extract of *Plumeria rubra* was added to 90 ml of 5 mM CuSO₄, and it was mixed and allowed to stand at room temperature until further colour change. An indicator for the synthesis of nanoparticles, the colour change was compared with the leaf extract of *Plumeria rubra* and 5 mM copper sulphate as a control solution.

For the synthesis of ZnO NPs, 100 ml of aqueous leaf extract was added to 1g of zinc nitrate hexahydrate and was stirred for 4 hours at 80°C. The solution mixture was cooled at room temperature, and the supernatant was discarded. The obtained pale white precipitate was centrifuged at 4500 rpm for 15 minutes. The obtained precipitate was dried at 80°C for 7 to 8 hours. The crude pellets were resuspended in double-distilled water, filtered, and stored at 4°C in the dark prior to their use.

4.2 UV-visible spectra analysis

The bioreduction of CuONPs and ZnONPs was monitored by sampling the reaction mixture at regular intervals, and the absorption maxima were scanned by UV-vis spectra, at the wavelength of 200-900 nm in a Shimadzu 1800 spectrophotometer operated at a resolution of 1 nm. Copper oxide (CuO) and zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles exhibit unique and tunable optical properties on account of their surface plasmon resonance (SPR), dependent on shape, size, and size distribution (Tripathi *et al.*, 2009). The solution mixture was subjected to centrifugation at 5,000 rpm for 15 min; the resulting pellet was dissolved in distilled water and filtered through a 0.22 µm Millipore filter. The process of centrifugation and redispersion in

sterile distilled water was repeated three times to ensure better separation of free entities from the metal nanoparticles.

4.3 X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD)

The structural characterization of the nanoparticles was determined using an X-ray diffractometer (X'pert PRO, PAN Analytical, Netherlands). A smear of the centrifuged and dried CuONPs and ZnONPs was used for X-ray diffraction studies. The X-ray generator was operated at 40 kV and 30 mA, wherein the samples were subjected to Cu radiation at a speed of 5° per min and drive axis of 2 (Mouxing *et al.*, 2006). This diffraction pattern is used to identify the crystalline phases of specimens, measure their structural properties, size, and orientation of these crystallines. XRD can also determine concentration profiles, film thickness, and atomic arrangements in amorphous materials and multilayers.

4.4 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

To determine the functional groups present on *Plumeria rubra* as well as *Rivinia humilis*. The powder was studied for its involvement in the synthesis of CuO and ZnO nanoparticles. FTIR analysis was carried out as described by Bankar *et al.*, 2010. *Plumeria rubra* and *Rivinia humilis* powder before (Control) and after reaction with copper sulphate and zinc nitrate (Test sample) were independently dried and blended with KBr to obtain a pellet. The FTIR spectra were collected at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ in the transmission mode using a Thermo Scientific Nicolet 380 FTIR spectrophotometer. The FTIR spectrum of a compound is the superposition of absorption bands of specific functional groups.

4.5 Scanning electron microscope (FESEM) and Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX)

The SEM analysis is based upon a beam of high-energy electrons, which generate a variety of signals at the surface of solid specimens. The signals that derive from electron sample interactions reveal information about the sample, including external morphology (texture), chemical composition, and crystalline structure and orientation of materials making up the sample. In most applications, data were collected over a selected area of the surface of the sample, and two-dimensional images were generated that display spatial variations in these properties. Areas ranging from approximately 1 cm to 5 microns in width were imaged in a scanning mode using conventional SEM techniques (magnification ranging from 20x to approximately 30,000x, spatial resolution of 50 to 500 nm). The SEM was used to perform analysis of selected point locations on the sample (JEOL, Model JFC-1600).

5.0 Bioassays

5.1 Determination of threshold time for the lethal effect of nanoparticles, chemicals, and plant extracts

Toxicity assays were performed to determine the threshold time for the lethal effect of nanoparticles, chemicals, and plant extracts on fourth instar larvae of *A. aegypti* by exposing them to a higher concentration of the extracts. The experiment was performed in triplicate.

5.2 Dose response bioassay

The aqueous leaf extract of *Plumeria rubra* and *Rivinia humilis* was lyophilized at - 20°C. Then, 10 mg of aqueous leaf extract of *Plumeria rubra* and *Rivinia humilis* was dissolved in 1 ml of distilled water for bioassay test of the plant extract (stock solution), 10 mg

of CuSO₄ and ZnNO₃ was dissolved in 1 ml of Milli Q water, 10 mg of synthesized CuONPs and ZnONPs was dissolved in 1 ml of Milli Q water (stock solution). From the stock solution, the aqueous leaf extract, chemical, as well as nanoparticle solutions were diluted using Milli Q water according to the desired concentrations (3.125, 6.25, 12.5, 25, and 50 mg/l). Each test included a set control group (distilled water) with three replicates for each individual concentration. The numbers of dead larvae were counted after 2, 4, 6, 24, and 48 hrs of exposure, and the percentage of mortality was reported from the average of three replicates.

5.3 Larvicidal assay

Larvicidal activity was assessed by the procedure of WHO (1998) with a few modifications as per the method of Rahuman *et al.* (2008). For the bioassay tests, larvae were sorted out into five batches of 20 in 249 ml of water and 1.0 ml of the desired sample concentration. Twenty individuals of fourth instar larvae of *A. aegypti* were introduced into the test containers.

- (i) Percentage of mortality is as follows:

$$\frac{\text{No.of dead larvae}}{\text{No.of larvae introduced}} \times 100$$

- (ii) Corrected percentage of mortality is as follows:

$$\frac{1-n \text{ in T after treatment}}{N \text{ in C after treatment}} \times 100$$

Where n is the number of larvae, T is the number of larvae that survived in the treated, and C is the number of larvae that survived in the control.

Note: The corrected percentage mortality value of each concentration was considered to estimate LC₅₀ values using SPSS probit analysis statistical pack, version 32.0.

6.0. Experimental design

The *Aedes aegypti* larvae were divided into seven groups of twenty animals each: -

- Group I : Control.
- Group II : Larvae treated with CuONPs upon 24 and 48 hr exposure.
- Group III : Larvae treated with ZnO NPs upon 24 and 48 hr exposure.
- Group IV : Larvae treated with CuSO₄ upon 24 and 48 hr exposure.
- Group V : Larvae treated with ZnNO₃ upon 24 and 48 hr exposure.
- Group VI : Larvae treated with *P. rubra* upon 24 and 48 hr exposure.
- Group VII : Larvae treated with *R. humilis* upon 24 and 48 hr exposure.

7.0. Preparation of whole-body homogenate

Both live control and treated adults were collected from the treated bottle. The live fourth instar larvae at 24 and 48 hrs were washed with double-distilled water, and the adhering water was removed completely by using blotting paper. Whole body homogenate was prepared using 10 insects in 500µl of 20 mM ice-cold sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.0, using an Eppendorf homogenizer, and then it was centrifuged at 12,000rpm for 10 mins. The supernatant was used as a crude enzyme source for further analysis. All glassware and buffers were kept at 4°C before use, and homogenizations of insects were done in cold conditions until the enzymes were stored at -20°C. For histopathological studies, the larvae were preserved immediately in neutral buffered formalin.

8.0. Quantitative analysis of biochemical constituents

The impact of insects on different nanoparticles, chemical, and aqueous extract exposure was quantitatively analysed with respect to any change in the levels of protein as well as the activities of five marker enzymes.

8.1 Estimation of protein

Protein content was estimated by the method of Lowry *et al.* (1951).

- 1 N NaOH : 4 g of NaOH were dissolved in 100 ml of double-distilled water.
- 0.1 N NaOH : 10 ml of 1N NaOH solution was made up to 100 ml with double-distilled water.
- Reagent A : 1 g of sodium carbonate was dissolved in 100 ml of 0.1N NaOH.
- Reagent B : 100 mg of sodium tartrate and 50 mg of cupric sulphate (CuSO₄.5H₂O) were dissolved successively in 10 ml of sterile distilled water.
- Reagent C : 2 ml of Reagent B was mixed with 100 ml of Reagent A.
- 1N Folin-phenol Reagent : 2 N Folin-phenol was diluted with an equal volume of double-distilled water.
- Protein standard : 1 mg of bovine serum albumin (BSA) was dissolved in 1 ml of 1N NaOH (1 mg/ml).

Note: All reagents were freshly prepared prior to protein determination.

To 10 µl of sample, 990 µl of double-distilled water, 5 ml of reagent C were added, and were incubated for 10 mins. To this, 0.5 ml of folin-phenol reagent was added, and the solution was again incubated for 20 mins. The absorbance was measured at 500nm in a Shimadzu UV

spectrophotometer. Aliquots of standard protein were also treated similarly, and the values were expressed in mg/ml.

$$\text{Protein concentration in the sample (mg/ml)} = \frac{\text{OD of the sample}}{\text{OD of the standard}} \times \text{Concentration of the standard} \times \text{Conversion factor}$$

8.2 Estimation of acetyl cholinesterase activity

The acetylcholinesterase activity in the whole body homogenates was measured according to Ellman *et al.* (1961), as described by Ikezawa & Taguchi (1981).

Principle and protocol

Acetylcholinesterase (AchE) hydrolyses acetylthiocholine, resulting in the formation of thiocholine. The enzyme activity was measured based on the formation of yellow colour due to the reaction of thiocholine with 5, 5-dithiobis-2-nitrobenzoic acid (DTNB), forming a yellow derivative 5-thio-2-nitrobenzoic acid, in which DTNB is a sensitive indicator for SH-groups.

For quantitative assay of AchE, 100 μl of larval homogenate was added to 800 μl of 100 mM sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7.5) and mixed well. To this mixture, 50 μl of DTNB reagent was added, and then the enzyme activity was initiated by adding 50 μl of substrate, acetylthiocholine iodide (12.5 mM). The reaction mixture was incubated for 5 min at room temperature, and the optical density of the yellow colour developed in the sample was read in a Shimadzu UV-160A spectrophotometer at 400 nm against a concurrently incubated blank

consisting of the same reagents and buffer substituted for the sample. The acetylcholinesterase activity was expressed as μM acetylthiocholine hydrolysed / minute.

AChE activity was calculated using the following formula:

$$R = \frac{\text{OD value of the sample}}{\text{Molecular extinction coefficient (13,600)}}$$

Where, R = mole of acetylthiocholine iodide hydrolyzed/minute
13,600 = Molecular extinction coefficient of DTNB.

8.3 Estimation of carboxylesterase activity

The carboxyl esterase activity in the whole body homogenate was measured by the modified method of Van Asperen (1962) as described by Argentine and James (1995).

Principle and protocol

α - or β -naphthol released by the action of esterase on α - or β -naphthyl acetate was coupled to the diazonium salt, resulting in the formation of an azo dye whose optical density was determined spectrophotometrically.

(a) Preparation of a standard graph for α -naphthyl

100 μl of α -naphthyl solutions at various concentrations of 100 to 500 μM were taken in individual Eppendorf tubes. 1 ml of 20 mM sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) and 400 μl of freshly prepared 0.3% Fast blue B in 3.3% sodium lauryl sulphate (SDS) were successively added to each tube and mixed well. After keeping for 15 minutes at room temperature, the

optical density of black colour developed in each standard solution was read at 430 nm against a blank (consisting of phosphate buffer and Fast blue B in 3.3% SDS solution) in a Shimadzu UV-160A spectrometer. A standard graph was prepared by plotting various test concentrations of α -naphthol against their respective optical density.

(b) *α -carboxylesterase activity*

100 μ l of larval whole body homogenate was incubated with 1 ml of 20mM sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) containing 250 μ M of α -naphthyl acetate for 30 min at room temperature. After incubation, 400 μ l of freshly prepared 0.3% Fast blue B in 3.3% SDS was added to stop the enzymatic reaction, and allowed to develop a black colour density in samples, and was read at 430 nm against the blank consisting of the same reagents and buffer substituted for the homogenate. The level of α -carboxylase activity was calculated using the standard graph and expressed as μ M α -naphthol released per minute.

(c) *Preparation of a standard graph for β -naphthol*

100 μ l of β -naphthol solutions at various concentrations (0.125 to 1.000 mM) were taken in individual Eppendorf tubes. One ml of sodium phosphate buffer (20 mM; pH 7.0) and 400 μ l of freshly prepared 0.3% fast blue B in 3.3% SDS were successively added to each tube and mixed well. After incubation for 15 min at room temperature, the optical density of red colour developed in each standard solution was read at 430 nm against a blank (consisting of phosphate buffer and Fast blue B in 3.3 % SDS solution) in a Shimadzu UV-160A spectrophotometer. A standard graph was prepared by plotting various test concentrations of β -naphthol against their respective optical density.

(d) *β -carboxylesterase activity*

The larval whole body homogenate was first diluted three times with sodium phosphate buffer (20 mM; pH 7.0), and 100 µl of diluted homogenate was incubated with one ml of sodium phosphate buffer (20mM; pH 7.0) containing 250 µM of β-naphthyl acetate for 30 min at room temperature. After incubation, 400 µl of freshly prepared 0.3% Fast blue B in 3.3% SDS was added to stop the enzymatic reaction and allowed to develop red colour for 15 minutes at room temperature. Blank consisted of the same reagents and buffer instead of the homogenate. The optical density of samples was read at 600 nm against the blank. The level of β-carboxylesterase activity was calculated using the standard graph and expressed as µM β-naphthol released per minute.

Carboxylase activity calculated using the following formula:

$$R = \frac{\text{OD of the sample}}{\text{Period of incubation}} \div \text{Protein concentration in sample} \times 1000$$

$$R = \mu\text{M of } \alpha \text{ or } \beta\text{-naphthol released per minute/ mg of protein}$$

8.4 Estimation of alkaline phosphatase activity

The alkaline phosphatase activity in the whole body homogenate was measured according to the modified procedure of Asakura (1978).

(a) Preparation of a standard graph for p-nitrophenol

Aliquots of 50 µl of p-nitrophenol solution at various concentrations (0.312 to 5.000 mM) were taken in individual Eppendorf tubes. 950 µl of acetate-acetic acid buffer (pH 4.0 or 4.6) or Tris-HCl buffer (pH 8.0) was added to each tube and mixed well. The mixture was incubated for 15 min at 37°C in a water bath, and then 100 µl of 0.5N NaOH solution was added to each tube. All

the tubes were centrifuged, and the optical density of yellow colour developed in the supernatant was read at 440 nm in a Shimadzu UV-160A spectrophotometer against a blank, which consisted of the respective buffer and 0.5N NaOH solutions. A standard graph was prepared by plotting various test concentrations of *p*-nitrophenol by measuring its optical density at 440 nm.

(b) Alkaline phosphatase activity

The levels of alkaline phosphatase activity in the fourth instar larvae of *A. aegypti* were estimated by mixing 20 µl of larval homogenate, which was made up to 500 µl with Tris-HCl buffer (50 mM, pH 8.0), and 500 µl of *p*-nitrophenyl phosphate buffer was added to the sample. The reaction mixture was incubated for 15 min at 37°C in a water bath. The enzymatic reaction was stopped by adding 100 µl of 0.5N NaOH solution. The mixture was centrifuged at 4000 x *g* for 5 minutes, and the optical density of the resulting clear supernatant was read at 440 nm in a Shimadzu UV 160A spectrophotometer against a suitable blank, which consisted of appropriate volumes of substrate solution and respective buffer substituted for the sample, and was concurrently processed along with the test samples. The alkaline phosphatase activity was calculated using the standard graph and expressed as mM *p*-nitrophenol liberated per minute.

9.0 Histopathological studies

The larvae in the treatment and control were fixed in neutral buffered formalin. The tissues were dehydrated with ethyl alcohol for 5 hrs, after which they were placed in xylene for tissue clearing. They were then embedded and blocked by paraplast and sectioned with a microtome. Sections were stained using haematoxylin and eosin according to routine staining methods. Untreated larvae were also investigated in the same manner (Kaewngang *et al.*, 2011).

10. Statistical analysis

Mean percent larval mortality data were subjected to analysis of variance and compared with Duncan's multiple range tests to determine any differences between plant species and within species and concentration (SPSS, 2007). LC_{50} and their associated confidence intervals were estimated from 24-h concentration mortality data using probit analysis (Finney, 1971). Lethal concentration at the 50% and slope levels were considered significantly different if their associated confidence intervals did not overlap. There was a strong relationship between the doses and death rate of parasites, as shown in the linear correlation (r^2), and all differences were considered significant if $P \leq 0.05$.

III. RESULTS

1.0 Phytochemical screening

The aqueous extract of *Plumeria rubra* revealed the presence of flavonoids, saponins, terpenoids, and reducing sugars (Table 1). The aqueous extract of *R. humilis* showed the presence of alkaloids, flavanoids, saponins, terpenoids, and reducing sugars (Table 2).

2.0 Synthesis of copper nanoparticles by using aqueous leaf extract of *P. rubra* and *R. humilis*

The visual observation of aqueous leaf extract of *P. rubra* was dark brown in colour before the addition of copper sulphate solution. After the addition of copper sulphate solution, the colour of the solution turned pale yellow. The colour of the extract further changed to greenish yellow, and later it changed to pale yellow after two hours of incubation, after which no significant change occurred (Fig. 1a).

Reduction of zinc ions into zinc oxide nanoparticles on exposure to aqueous leaf extract of *R. humilis* resulted in precipitation. Clear $ZnNO_3$ changed into precipitate due to the excitation of surface plasmon resonance (SPR), which indicates the formation of zinc oxide nanoparticles (Fig.1b).

3.0 UV spectra analysis

Absorption spectrum of synthesized CuONPs at different wavelengths ranging from 200 to 900 nm revealed a peak at 790 nm, indicating formation of CuONPs (Fig. 2a). The absorption

spectra of synthesized zinc oxide nanoparticles with leaf aqueous extract of *R. humilis* at wavelengths ranging from 200 to 900 nm revealed a sharp surface plasmon resonance (SPR) at 369 nm, indicating the formation of zinc oxide nanoparticles (Fig. 2b).

4.0 Fourier transform infrared resonance (FTIR) analysis

FTIR has often been used as an essential tool in determining specific functional groups or chemical bonds that exist in a material. The presence of a peak at a specific wave number would indicate the presence of a specific chemical bond.

The FTIR spectra using CuONPs synthesized by green synthesis showed an absorption spectrum indicating the presence of nanoparticles. The peaks were obtained at 618.74, 1102.22, 1405.39, 1632.59, 2849.95, 2919.36, and 3421.07 cm^{-1} , respectively. The peak at 3421.07 corresponds to O-H and N-H stretching. The peak at 2919.36 corresponds to the O-H and C-H stretch. The peak at 2849.95 corresponds to the stretching vibration of the =C-H stretch of the aldehyde. The peak at 1632.59 corresponds to the C=C of the alkene. The peak 1405.39 corresponds to -C-H stretch, C=C stretch of alkane and aromatic groups. The peak at 1102.22 corresponds to the C-O, C-F, C-N, and C-O stretch of ether, anhydride, alcohol, amine, and alkyl halide. The peak at 618.74 corresponds to the C-C stretch of alkyl halide (Fig. 3a).

The FTIR spectra for the aqueous extract of *Plumeria rubra* resulted in various peaks at 617.99, 1081.30, 1400.33, 1630.24, and 3421.60 cm^{-1} , respectively. The peak at 617.99 corresponds to the C-C stretching of the alkyl halide group. The peak at 1081.30 corresponds to the N-H stretching of the amide. The peak at 1400.33 corresponds to -C-H, C-F, and C=C stretching of alkane, alkyl halide, and aromatic. The peak at 1630.24 corresponds to the N-H

stretching of the amide. The peak at 3421.60 corresponds to O-H and N-H stretching of alcohol, amine, and amide (Fig. 3a).

The FTIR spectra of ZnONPs synthesized by green synthesis showed an absorption spectrum indicating the presence of nanoparticles. The peaks were obtained at 618.81, 1105.31, 1322.59, 1640.86, 2920.93, and 3416.88 cm^{-1} . The peak at 3416.88 corresponds to the O-H and N-H stretch of alcohol, amine, and amide. The peak at 2920.93 corresponds to the O-H and C-H stretch of alkane and acid groups. The peak at 1640.86 corresponds to stretching vibration of C=C of the alkene and the bending vibration of the amide. The peak at 1322.59 corresponds to the C-F stretch and N-H stretch of the amine. The peak at 1105.31 corresponds to the C-O, C-F, and C-N stretch of alcohol, alkyl halide, and amine. The peak at 618.81 corresponds to the C-Cl stretch of alkyl halide (Fig. 3b).

The FTIR spectra for the aqueous extract of *Rivina humilis* resulted in various peaks at 462.91, 620.95, 820.62, 1025.09, 1317.57, 1363.44, 1383.83, 1653.33, 1904.71, and 3388.35. The peak at 3388.35 corresponds to the O-H stretch of alcohol. The peak at 1653.33 corresponds to stretching vibration of C=C of alkene. The peak at 1383.83 corresponds to the -C-H stretch of alkane. The peak at 1363.44 corresponds to the -C-H stretch of alkane. The peak at 1317.57 corresponds to the C-F and -C-N stretch of alkyl halide and amine. The peak at 1025.09 corresponds to the C-F, C-O, and C-O stretch of alkyl halide, ester, and ether. The peak at 820.62 corresponds to =C-H bending vibration of alkene (Fig. 3b).

5.0 XRD analysis

X-ray diffraction patterns showed diffraction peaks associated with copper oxide metal at (110), (111), (022), and (311), respectively. The observed diffraction reflection was compared

with ICSD- 087122 and is attributed to the face-centered cubic structure of CuO nanoparticles with monoclinic phase. A typical monoclinic structure, and no extra peaks were observed. Well-defined and sharp CuO reflections were observed in XRD patterns, which verify the well-crystalline nature of CuONPs using the Scherer formula (Fig. 4a).

X-ray diffraction patterns showed enhanced crystallinity effect with diffraction peaks associated with zinc oxide metal at (100), (002), (101), (102), (110), and (112), respectively. The observed diffraction reflection was compared with JCPDS No. 89-7102 and is attributed to bulk ZnO materials. Well-defined ZnO reflections were observed in XRD patterns, which verify the well-crystalline nature of ZnONPs, Scherer formula (Fig. 4b).

6.0 FESEM with EDX analysis

The morphology and size of the nanoparticles in the solution are determined by SEM images. The CuONPs nanoparticles were large, uniform, with well-defined spherical morphology lacking mono-dispersity (Fig. 5a; A & B). The composition of biosynthesized CuONPs was studied under energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). The EDX spectrum displays only Cu and O peaks without any impurity peaks, revealing that the biosynthesized nanomaterials are composed of Cu and O elements. This qualitative data confirms the formation of CuO nanoparticles in the sample (Fig. 5a; C).

FESEM analysis was performed based on a topological study in which the ZnONPs were found to be smooth and rectangular in shape (Fig. 5 b; A & B). The energy dispersive spectroscopic analysis displayed only Zn and O peaks without any impurity peaks, revealing that the biosynthesized nanomaterials are composed of Zn and O elements, indicating the presence of biosynthesized zinc oxide nanoparticles (Fig. 5b; C).

7.0 Determination of threshold time for lethal effect of nanoparticles, chemicals, and plant extracts on fourth instar larvae of *Aedes aegypti*

As shown in Figure 6, there was no mortality in the control, showing 0% mortality at 24 and 48 hr. The CuONPs did not inflict mortality up to 6 h, but at 24 h approximately. 86.7 % mortality was observed, and at 48 hr, 98.4% mortality was seen, whereas in the case of ZnONPs, approx.70% mortality was observed. Further, at 48 hr, 83.4% mortality was seen, which indicates the toxicity of CuONPs over ZnONPs when treated with 4th instar larvae of *A. aegypti*. In the case of CuSO₄, 73.4 % mortality was seen at 24 hr. Further, at 48 hr, 83.4% mortality was seen upon treatment, whereas in treatment with ZnNO₃ at 24 hr, 66.7 % mortality was observed, and at 48 hr, 73.4 % mortality was observed, indicating that CuSO₄ is toxic compared to ZnNO₃ but has a lesser effect when compared to CuONPs. *P. rubra* treated larvae showed 56.7% mortality at 24 h, and 48 hr it showed 65 % mortality, whereas in the case of *R. humilis* treated larvae it showed 53.4 % mortality at 24 h, and at 48 hr it showed 61.7 % mortality, indicating that *P. rubra* is more toxic when compared to *R. humilis* and has a lesser effect when compared to CuSO₄ and CuONPs.

8.0 Determination of lethal concentrations of nanoparticles, chemicals, and plant extracts on fourth instar larvae of *Aedes aegypti*

The two synthesized nanoparticles, chemicals, as well as plant sources, were tested sequentially against 4th instar larvae of *A. aegypti*. As presented in Table 3, among the six different compositions, it was found that the CuONP exhibited 98% mortality at the highest concentration against *A. aegypti*. The corresponding LC₅₀ value for 24 hr was 17.43 mg/ml. This

extract at 48 hr exposure gave an LC₅₀ value of 6.96 mg/ml. It also implies the potent lethal effect of CuONPs towards vector control when compared to the chemical CuSO₄. In the case of CuSO₄ treated 4th instar larvae of *Aedes aegypti*, it exhibited 73.4% mortality with an LC₅₀ value of 12.28 mg/ml at 24 and 48 hr, and it exhibited 83.3% mortality with an LC₅₀ value of 5.78 mg/ml. Whereas in the case of *P. rubra* treated 4th instar larvae of *Aedes aegypti*, it exhibited 56.7% mortality with an LC₅₀ value of 9.33 mg/ml at 24 and 48 hr. It exhibited a 65% mortality with an LC₅₀ value of 22.93 mg/ml, showing a lesser effect when compared to CuSO₄ and CuONPs.

In the case of ZnONPs, it was found to possess 83% mortality at the highest concentration when compared to the chemical and plant extract. The corresponding LC₅₀ value was 18.60 mg/ml at 24 hr, and at 48 hr exposure, the LC₅₀ value was 12.12 mg/ml. In the case of ZnNO₃ treated 4th instar larvae of *Aedes aegypti* it exhibited 66.7% mortality with an LC₅₀ value of 11.70 mg/ml at 24 hr and a 73.4% mortality with an LC₅₀ value of 8.101 mg/ml at 48 hr showing that ZnONPs have better effect when compared to ZnNO₃ whereas in the case of *R. humilis* treated 4th instar larvae of *Aedes aegypti* it exhibited 53.4% mortality with an LC₅₀ value of 23.64 mg/ml at 24 hr and exhibited a 61.7% mortality with an LC₅₀ value of 15.6 mg/ml at 48 hr showing lesser effect when compared to ZnNO₃ and ZnONPs.

9.0 Determination of threshold time for lethal effect of nanoparticles, chemicals, and plant extracts on fourth instar larvae of *Chironomous costatus*

As shown in Figure 7, there was no mortality in the control, showing 0% mortality at 24 and 48 h. The synthesized CuONPs showed 3.4 % and 13.4 % mortality at 24 and 48 hr, whereas the synthesized ZnONPs showed 16.7 % and 30 % mortality at 24 and 48 hr. CuONPs didn't

affect their normal behaviour at 24 hr, indicating non-toxicity of nanoparticles towards non-target organisms such as *C. costatus*. Further, the chemicals such as CuSO₄ showed 86.7 and 100% mortality at 24 and 48 hr, and ZnNO₃ showed 43.4 and 63.4 % mortality at 24 and 48 hr, indicating that CuSO₄ affects the stability of the organism. When treated with *P. rubra*, it showed 3.4 and 16.7 % mortality at 24 and 48 h. *R. humilis* showed 13.4 and 23.4 % mortality at 24 and 48 hr, proving that it is less toxic when compared to the chemicals such as CuSO₄.

10.0 Determination of lethal concentrations of nanoparticles, chemicals, and plant extracts on fourth instar larvae of *Chironomous costatus*

As shown in Table 4, the corresponding LC₅₀ value for CuONPs treated *C. costatus* was 125.60 mg/ml and 87.60 mg/ml at 24 and 48 hr. The LC₅₀ value for CuSO₄ treated *C. costatus* was 10.91 mg/ml at and 10.52 mg/ml at 24 and 48 hr, whereas the LC₅₀ value for *P. rubra* treated *C. costatus* was 125.60 mg/ml at 24 hr and 79.23 mg/ml at 48 hr.

The corresponding LC₅₀ value for ZnONPs-treated *C. costatus* was 83.83 mg/ml and 69.05mg/ml at 24 and 48 hr. The LC₅₀ value for ZnNO₃ treated *C. costatus* was 49.84 mg/ml and 33.91 mg/ml at 24 and 48 hr, whereas the LC₅₀ value for *R. humilis* treated *C. costatus* was 87.60 mg/ml and 91.95 mg/ml at 24 and 48 hr, which shows that CuONPs, ZnONPs, *P. rubra*, and *R. humilis* were less toxic compared to chemical CuSO₄ and ZnNO₃.

11.0 Histological analysis

The body of the mosquito larva is morphologically differentiated into head, thorax, and 10 externally visible abdominal segments. Internally, the digestive system is divided into three parts, namely the stomodeum or foregut, mesenteron or midgut, and proctodeum or hindgut.

The histopathological results revealed that the groups II to V showed disruption predominantly in the midgut region, damage in the siphon area, columnar epithelial cells, and the cells got detached from the gut lining when compared to control animals (group I: Figs. 8 &9).

12.0 Quantitative analysis

12.1 Effect of synthesized nanoparticles, chemicals, as well as plant sources, on the protein level of *Aedes aegypti* larvae

The crude protein level from the whole body homogenate of fourth instar larvae in group I during their normal course showed a maximum level at 24 and 48 hr when compared to the treated groups II-VII, which showed a significant decrease in protein value at 24 and 48 hr, respectively (Fig. 10).

The nanoparticle-treated groups II and III showed no significant changes in the protein value when compared to chemical-treated groups IV and V. Aqueous extracts treated groups VI and VII showed a moderate decrease in protein value when compared to nanoparticles and chemical-treated groups.

12.2 Effect of synthesized nanoparticles, chemicals, as well as plant sources on acetylcholinesterase activity in *Aedes aegypti* larvae

As shown in the figure. 11, AchE levels decreased significantly in groups II to V animals that were administered with synthesized nanoparticles as well as chemicals alone at 24 and 48 hr when compared to control larvae (group I). Whereas, both aqueous extract-treated groups VI and VII were similar to that of the control larvae (group I).

12.3 Effect of synthesized nanoparticles, chemicals, as well as aqueous extract on carboxylesterase activity in larvae

12.3.1 α -carboxylesterase activity

As shown in the figure. 12, the α -carboxylesterase level decreased significantly in groups II to V larvae that were administered with synthesized nanoparticles as well as chemicals alone at and 48 hr when compared to control larvae (group I). Whereas, both aqueous extract-treated group VI and VII were similar to that of the control group I ($P>0.05$).

As shown in the figure. 13, the level of β -carboxylesteraseis decreased in the treated groups II to V at both 24 and 48 hr when compared to control larvae (group I), but the aqueous extract-treated groups VI and VII were similar to that of control group I ($P>0.05$).

12.4 Effect of synthesized nanoparticles, chemicals, as well as aqueous extract on phosphatase activity in larvae

12.4.1 Alkaline phosphatase activity

As shown in the figure. 14, alkaline phosphatase levels decreased significantly in groups II to V animals that were administered with synthesized nanoparticles as well as chemicals alone at 24 and 48 hr when compared to control larvae (group I). Whereas, both aqueous extract-treated groups VI and VII were similar to that of the control larvae (group I).

IV. DISCUSSION

Plants are a source of secondary metabolites responsible for a wide range of biological activities, including anti-mosquitocidal properties. Earlier studies have proven the effect of diverse plant species having potential effects on both larvae and pupal stages of mosquitoes (Changsang *et al.*, 2005; Khanna and Kannabiran, 2007), indicating that the secondary metabolites play a major role in the control of various developmental stages of mosquito larvae. We chose two plants, *P. rubra* and *R. humilis*, for our study, in which tannins, saponins, flavanoids, reducing sugars, terpenoids, and alkaloids were present in the leaves of *P. rubra*, whereas in *R. humilis*, it was reported to possess secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, flavanoids, saponins, terpenoids, and reducing sugars (Egwaikhide *et al.*, 2009).

In our study, we tested *P. rubra* and *R. humilis* aqueous extracts against the 4th instar of *A. aegypti* larvae. The aqueous extract of *P. rubra* showed 56% mortality at the highest concentration at 24 hr exposure, whereas the aqueous extract of *R. humilis* showed 53% mortality at the highest concentration at 24 hr exposure. It was notable that the effective concentration of this extract is required to produce 100% mortality. However, the LC₅₀ value increased upon further exposure, but did not have a significant impact on sustained larvicidal effect. Therefore, we used both plant sources for the production of biologically synthesized nanoparticles, which could enhance the toxic potential during prolonged exposure.

Based on previous literature, it has been noted that changes in the colour of the solution indicate the formation of copper oxide nanoparticles. In the UV-vis spectrophotometer, the absorbance spectrum was observed at 327 nm (Fig. 2a). This may be due to excitation of longitudinal plasma vibrations (Abdoud *et al.*, 2014; Sharma *et al.*, 2015). Similar reports for UV-vis spectrophotometer using the leaves extract from Aloe vera were observed CuONPs peaks

at 265 to 285nm (Kumar *et al.*, 2001). The synthesized zinc oxide nanoparticles show absorption spectra at 389 nm (Fig. 2b). Thus, the peak indicates the formation of zinc oxide nanoparticles. It has been reported that leaf extracts of *Azadirachta indica*, *Cassia alata*, *Parthenium hysterophorus*, *Aloe barbabensis*, and *Tabernaemontana divaricata* were reduced to zinc oxide, and it was revealed that the 377, 320, 374, 375, 350 to 410 nm range of peaks was observed in leaf extract through a spectrophotometer (Bhuya *et al.*, 2015; Happy *et al.*, 2017; Rajiv *et al.*, 2013; Sangeetha *et al.*, 2011; Raja *et al.*, 2018).

FTIR analysis indicates the presence of various functional groups in both plant extracts and biosynthesized nanoparticles. The peaks were obtained at 618.74, 1102.22, 1405.39, 1632.59, 2849.95, 2919.36, 3421.07 cm^{-1} , respectively (Fig. 3a). The similar FTIR peak reports revealed a formation of CuONPs, which were located at 1100, 524, and 350 cm^{-1} , corresponding to hydroxyl groups, alkenes, and alkanes. The formation of CuONPs was confirmed by FTIR analysis using gum karaya and *Tridax procumbens* leaf extract (Padil *et al.*, 2013; Kabali *et al.*, 2018). The FTIR spectra of ZnONPs synthesized by green synthesis showed an absorption spectrum indicating the presence of nanoparticles. The peaks were obtained at 618.81, 1105.31, 1322.59, 1640.86, 2920.93, and 3416.88 cm^{-1} (Fig. 3b). Similar reports for FTIR were shown in *Azadirachta indica*, *Cassia alata*, *Parthenium hysterophorus*, *Aloe barbabensis*, *Catharanthus roseus*, and *Tabernaemontana divaricata* leaf extracts for synthesized zinc oxide nanoparticles (Bhuya *et al.*, 2015; Happy *et al.*, 2019; Rajiv *et al.*, 2013; Sangeetha *et al.*, 2011; Yedurkar *et al.*, 2016; Raja *et al.*, 2018).

The XRD revealed the crystalline structure of nanoparticles. The XRD diffraction patterns of CuONPs were at (110), (111), (022), and (311) (Fig. 4a). Similar reports were shown in *Aloe barbadensis*, *Bifurcaria bifurcate*, *Carica papaya*, *Calptropis gigantean*, and *Gloriosa*

superb leaf extract for synthesized copper oxide nanoparticles (Sangeetha *et al.*, 2011; Abdoud *et al.*, 2014; Renu *et al.*, 2014; Sharma *et al.*, 2015; Naika *et al.*, 2015). The XRD diffraction patterns of ZnONPs were at (100), (002), (101), (102), (110), and (112), respectively (Fig. 4b) and the reports were shown in *Azadirachta indica*, *Cassia alata*, *Parthenium hysterophorus*, *Aloe barbabensis*, *Catharanthus roseus*, and *Tabernaemontanadivariata* leaf extracts for synthesized zinc oxide nanoparticle (Bhuya *et al.*, 2015; Happy *et al.*, 2019; Rajiv *et al.*, 2013; Sangeetha *et al.*, 2011; Rajendran and Sengodan, 2017; Raja *et al.*, 2018)

The morphology and size of the nanoparticles in the solution were determined by SEM images. The CuONPs nanoparticles were large, uniform, with well-defined spherical morphology, lacking monodispersity. The EDX spectrum displays only Cu and O peaks without any impurities (Fig. 5a), confirming the presence of CuONPs. Similar reports for SEM with EDX were shown in *Aloe barbadensis*, *Gum karaya*, *Bifurcaria bifurcate*, *Carica papaya*, *Calptropis gigantean*, and *Gloriosa superb* leaf extract for synthesized copper oxide nanoparticles (Sangeetha *et al.*, 2012; Vinod *et al.*, 2014; Abdoud *et al.*, 2014; Renu *et al.*, 2014; Sharma *et al.*, 2015; Naika *et al.*, 2015). The energy dispersive spectroscopic analysis displayed only Zn and O peaks without any impurity peaks. This confirms the presence of ZnONPs (Fig. 5b). Similar reports for SEM with EDX were shown in *Atalantia monophylla*, *T. divaricata*, *Azadirachta indica* leaf extract for synthesized Zinc oxide nanoparticles, and in dry ginger (Kumar *et al.*, 2018; Raja *et al.*, 2018; Elumalai *et al.*, 2015; Janaki *et al.*, 2015).

Since mosquitoes are quite commonly held responsible for the distribution of major diseases like malaria, filariasis, dengue, chikungunya, and Japanese encephalitis, etc. Klemper *et al.* (2007) stated that it is a great challenge to control these vector-borne diseases. Therefore, we attempted to test these nanoparticles, which are said to be cost-effective and environmentally

safe agents (Shobha *et al.*, 2014). In this study, the CuONPs have shown 86% mortality at 24 hr. Further, at 48 hr it has shown 98% mortality with a LC₅₀ value of 17.43mg/ml and 6.96 mg/ml at 24 and 48 hr. Treatment with ZnONP has shown 70% mortality at 24 hr. Further, at 48 hr, it has shown 83% mortality with a LC₅₀ value of 18.60mg/ml and 12.12mg/ml at 24 and 48 hr.

Previous reports on larvicidal potential of CuONPs against *A. aegypti* larvae using the aqueous extract of *T. Procumbens*, *A. heterophyllus* were also reported (Kabali *et al.*, 2018; Sharon *et al.*, 2018), showing a potent effect of CuONPs. Banumathi *et al.* (2017) reported that plant species were used for the synthesis and stabilization of ZnO nanoparticles based on their maximum efficacy against third-instar larvae of *A. aegypti*. *L. Leschenaultiana*-encapsulated ZnO nanoparticles showed 100% mortality when tested at 10 mg/l.

Histological evidence also revealed changes in the morphology of the midgut cells and siphon area of *A. aegypti*, which were treated with the copper oxide nanoparticles as well as the zinc oxide nanoparticles. Similar results have also been reported in *A. aegypti* larvae treated with silver nanoparticles (Kalimuthu *et al.*, 2017)

In our study, the AChE levels decreased upon treatment with nanoparticles, indicating that it can be toxic via interactions with proteins and enzymes. Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) is a key enzyme present in the brain, blood, and nervous system. Adsorption and inhibition rates by nanoparticles were estimated by decrease of AChE activities compared to controls upon treatment with bulk Cu particles, AChE inhibition was primarily caused by dissolved ions, but mainly by adsorption for activated carbon this had a dose-response relationship showing that these nanoparticles may have neurotoxicity and AChE may have potential to be used as a biomarker for nanoparticles (Wang *et al.*, 2009).

In the present study, larvae exposed to CuONP and ZnONP showed a significant decrease in the levels of α and β -carboxylesterase activity. Evidences also suggest that a change in α and β -carboxylesterase upon inducing cadmium oxide nanoparticles in zebra fish causes inhibition of α -carboxylesterase and β -carboxylesterase activity when compared to control (Balmuri *et al.*, 2017).

In the case of alkaline phosphatase, the levels of *p*-nitrophenol liberated are reduced; the levels of *p*-nitrophenol seem to be higher when treated with CuONP and ZnONPs. Subsequently, investigators have also noted an increase in the activity of phytase acid and alkaline phosphatase in the rhizosphere due to nanoZnO sprayed on clusterbean plants, which might be due to ZnO nanoparticle, which acts as cofactors for phytase and phosphatase enzymes, which in turn help in the growth of plants (Raliya and Tarafdar, 2013).

Further in the present investigation, we attempted to check for the toxic effect of CuONPs and ZnONPs by evaluating the biochemical markers such as acetylcholine esterase, α , β carboxylesterase, and alkaline phosphatase activity, which are potential indicators of biocides. The levels of the protein were decreased when treated with nanoparticles, which indicates that CuONPs and ZnONPs can be used as potential biocides.

All the above findings, taken together, indicate that the exposure of larvae *A. aegypti* to the nanoparticles significantly affects the three important enzyme levels when compared to chemical and plant extracts.

V. SUMMARY

In the present investigation, we performed phytochemical screening of *Plumeria rubra* and *Rivinia humilis* aqueous leaf extracts, synthesized copper oxide and zinc oxide nanoparticles using these two plant extracts, and tested their potential mosquitocidal activity against the larvae (fourth instar) of disease-causing vector *A. aegypti*.

- Phytochemical screening of aqueous leaf extract of *P.rubra* and *R. humilis*, which indicated the presence of saponins, flavanoids, terpenoids, and reducing sugars, and they served as precursors for the synthesis and production of CuONPs and ZnONPs.
- The freshly prepared leaf extract of *P. rubra* appeared in dark brown colour upon the addition of copper sulphate solution, and it changed into pale yellow in colour. The reduction of CuONPs was observed using UV-vis spectroscopy and the surface plasma resonance with a distinct peak at 770 nm. On the other hand, UV-visible spectroscopy clearly indicates the synthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles with aqueous leaf extract of *R. humilis* with an absorption peak at 369 nm.
- FTIR spectra of synthesized CuONPs prepared using *P.rubra* leaf extract exhibited prominent peaks at 3421.07, 2919.36, 2849.95, 1632.59, 1405.39, 1102.22, and 618.74 cm^{-1} . The sharp absorption peak at 3421.07 cm^{-1} is assigned to the O-H stretch and alcohol group, which corresponds to the FTIR peak of *P. rubra* and synthesized ZnONPs from *R. humilis*. This preparation gave peaks at 3416, 2920, 1640, 1401, 1322, 1105, 618 cm^{-1} , thereby revealing the formation of ZnONPs, which was confirmed by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy.

- X-ray diffraction patterns determine diffraction peaks associated with copper oxide at (110), (111), (022), and (311), and zinc oxide at (100), (002), (101), (102), (110), and (112). Well-defined and sharp CuO reflections were observed in XRD patterns, demonstrating the well-crystalline nature of the nanoparticle for CuONPs and ZnONPs.
- SEM analysis of synthesized CuONPs and ZnONPs revealed a uniform, well-defined, and spherical morphology. The composition of biosynthesized nanoparticles was studied under EDX analysis, which displayed peaks without any impurity peaks, revealing that the biosynthesized nanoparticles are composed of Cu and O elements in CuONPs and Zn and O elements in ZnONPs.
- Larvicidal assays performed using sub-lethal concentrations of 12.5 mg/l copper oxide or zinc oxide nanoparticles showed a higher mortality rate of *A.aegypti* larvae at 24 and 48 hr.
- Histopathological analyses revealed that the morphological disruption in larvae's midgut and in the siphon area was observed in nanoparticles and chemically treated groups of larvae.
- Levels of protein, acetylcholinesterase, carboxylesterase, and alkaline phosphatase activities showed lowered levels in nanoparticles-treated groups when compared to other groups at 24 and 48 hr post-exposure.

The present study highlights that the nanoparticles and chemically treated groups show more toxicity in mosquito larvae, whereas biologically synthesized CuONPs and ZnONPs possess no toxic effect on non-target organisms, namely chironomous larvae.

VI. REFERENCES

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